

Thinking the Event

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Introduction

In the pages that follow, I will attempt to identify several features of the event which I explored in my recent book, *Thinking the Event* (2020). In this work, I have attempted a philosophical inquiry into what constitutes an event as an event, its very eventfulness: not *what* happens, not *why* it happens, but *that* it happens, and what “happening” mean: not the *eventum*, what has happened, but the *evenire*, the sheer happening of what happens. By the expression “thinking the event,” I do not mean the appropriation by thought of the event, under the authority of the principle of reason. Rather, “thinking the event” means to give thought to its very *eventfulness*, its sheer happening, which I suggest necessarily exceeds both reason and subjectivity. Indeed, one could say that the event, in its disruptive and unpredictable happening, *exceeds* both the concept and the anticipation of a subject. Such a project goes against the tradition that has always neutralized the event by anchoring it in a reason or a cause. Indeed, the concept of event has traditionally been understood and neutralized within a metaphysics of causality, subjectivity, and reason, in a word, subjected to the demands of rational thought. An event is interpreted either as the accident of a substrate or substance, as the effect or deed of a subject or an agent, or else it is ordered and organized according to causality, when it is not included within fate or a rational order. In all instances, it answers to the demands of the principle of sufficient reason, which states that no event happens without a cause or a reason. In the words of Leibniz (Leibniz and Clarke, 2000), the “great” principle of natural philosophy and key metaphysical principle of truth is “the *principle of sufficient reason*, namely, that nothing happens without a reason why it should be so rather than otherwise” (p. 7). Such reason can also be a cause, as the principle of sufficient reason merges with a “principle of causality,” which states that every event is caused to be the event that it is. Again, in Leibniz’s (Leibniz and Clarke, 2000) words: “Nothing is without reason, or no effect is without a cause” (Leibniz, cited in Heidegger [1991], p. 21).

However, as Heidegger (1991) demonstrates in his 1955-1956 lecture course *The Principle of Reason*, the principle of reason self-deconstructs, because it cannot apply to itself its own requirements without undermining itself: if the principle of reason states that everything that happens must have a reason, then what is the reason for the principle of reason? Does the principle of reason have a reason? “*Nihil est sine ratione*. Nothing is without reason, says the principle of reason. Nothing—which means not even this principle of reason, certainly it least of all. It may then be that the principle of reason, that whereof it speaks, and this speaking itself do not belong within the jurisdiction of the principle of reason. To think this remains a grave burden. In short it means that *the principle of reason is without reason*. Said still more clearly: ‘Nothing without reason’— *this, which is something, is without reason*” (p. 17; emphasis mine). One divines here how the principle of reason is caught in a circle (What is the reason of the principle of reason? What is the foundation of a foundation?) that throws it into an abyss, into the abyss of its own impossible foundation.

Indeed, in order to be a ground, the ground must itself be without foundation and therefore groundless! This led Gilles Deleuze (cited in Zourabichvili [2012]) to speak of the paradoxical nature of the logic of grounding, of the “comical ungrounding” of the principle of reason: “But who still speaks of a foundation, when the logic of grounding or the principle of reason leads precisely to its own ‘ungrounding,’ comical and disappointing” (p. 57). The principle of reason collapses (“runs aground”) at the very place of its impossible foundation, “there where,” as Derrida (2005b) puts it in *Rogues*, “the *Grund* opens up onto the *Abgrund*, where giving reasons [*rendre-raison*] and giving an account [*rendre-compte*]*—logon didonai* or *principium reddendae rationis**—*are threatened by or drawn into the abyss” (p. 122). The question “why,” the question seeking reasons, opens onto an abyss. As Heidegger (1991) argued, “Whenever we pursue the ground/reason of a being, we ask: why? Cognition stalks this interrogative word from one reason to another. The ‘why’ allows no rest, offers no stop, *gives no support*” (p. 126; my emphasis). The question ‘why,’ seeking a foundation, in fact undermines it. Reason is without reason, leading Derrida (2005) to ask: “The value of reason, the desire for reason, the dignity of reason—are these rational? Do these have to do wholly with reason?” (p. 120).

The Transcendental, the Event

Reason is thus exceeded from within, opening onto pure eventfulness, itself happening outside reason. In fact, each time unpredictable and incalculable, an event always exceeds or “suspends” (Marion, 2002a, p. 160) the principle of sufficient reason. As such, the event constitutes a challenge to reason and understanding. As Derrida (Derrida and Roudinesco [2004]), puts it, “The event is what comes and, in coming, comes to surprise me, to surprise and to suspend comprehension: the event is first of all *that which* I do not first of all comprehend. Better, the event is first of all *that* I do not comprehend. The fact that I do not comprehend: my incomprehension” (p. 50). This is why for Derrida it is not a matter of complying with the demands of the principle of reason, but instead of not “denying or ignoring this unforeseeable and incalculable coming of the other” (Derrida and Roudinesco [2004], p. 50). It is a matter of freeing eventfulness from the demands of the principle of reason. No longer placed under the authority of the principle of sufficient reason, the event must be rethought as the incalculable and unpredictable arrival of what will always remain other—and thus inappropriable—for the one to whom it happens. In that sense, the event also comes as an excess in relation to the subject, and can only “naturally take by surprise not only the addressee but also the subject to whom and by whom it is supposed to happen” (Derrida [2004], p. 60). It would then be a matter, in order to give thought to the event in its eventfulness, of freeing the event from the demands of the principle of sufficient reason, as well as from the predominance of transcendental modes of thought, which claim to provide prior conditions of possibility for the occurrence of events. Indeed, it may well be the case that events are precisely eventful when not pre-organized or prepared by some transcendental conditions, or anticipated by a transcendental subject, when they break or “pierce” the horizon provided by transcendental conditions. An event cannot be made possible by a prior condition, or rather, as Jean-Luc Nancy (2007) pointed out, it “must not be the object of a programmatic and certain calculation.... It must be the possibility of the impossible (according to a logic used often by Derrida), it must know itself as such, that is to say, know that it happens also in the incalculable and the unassignable” (p. 49). An event cannot be reduced to what *can* happen: it does not happen because it can happen, but rather happens without being made possible in advance and to that extent can be called “impossible,” Jean-Luc Marion (2015) going so far as to state that the event

can only be impossible, the impossible itself: “Moreover, [the event] always appears to us at bottom as impossible, or even as the impossible, since it does not belong to the domain of the possible, of that of which we are able” (p. 182). The impossible, in this context, does not mean what cannot be or happen. Rather, the impossible, or the im-possible, as Derrida writes it, means that which happens outside the conditions of possibility offered in advance by a subject of representation, outside the transcendental conditions of possibility. Thinking the event will require to break with a certain transcendental mode of thinking, as the event deconstructs the transcendental as such.

The event deconstructs the transcendental, the transcendental conditions of possibility, the “power” of the possible. In *Paper Machine*, Derrida (2005a) resituates his relation to the motif of the transcendental and to the expression “quasi-transcendental,” as discussed by Rodolphe Gasché: “it is definitely not by chance that the modality of quasi (or the logical-rhetorical fiction of as if) has so often imposed itself on me to make a word into a phrase, and first of all, especially—it has often been noted and commented on—around the word transcendental” (p. 83). At stake is a questioning of the tradition of the transcendental, of the very motif of the conditions of possibility. “A question of problematic context and strategies, presumably: one must in this place relentlessly reaffirm questions of the transcendental type; and in that place, almost simultaneously, also ask questions about the history and the limits of what is called ‘transcendental’” (Derrida [2005a], p. 83). Derrida does not simply want to do away with transcendental strategies (he is quite clear on this point), he instead seeks to question the transcendental and reorient it toward the “quasi,” the “impossible,” and the event: “For nothing can discredit the right to the transcendental or ontological question. This is the only force that resists empiricism and relativism. Despite appearances to which philosophers in a hurry often rush, nothing is less empiricist or relativist than a certain attention to the multiplicity of contexts and the discursive strategies they govern; than a certain insistence on the fact that a context is always open and nonsaturable; or than taking into account the perhaps and the quasi in thinking about the event” (Derrida [2005a], p. 92). Mentioning the transcendental “condition of possibility” “in all its forms: medieval onto-theology, criticism, or phenomenology” (Derrida [2005a], p. 92), Derrida shows that at issue is the traditional demand for conditions of possibility, that is, for a ground. In question is “the philosophical inheritance, namely the demand for the condition of possibility (the a priori, the originary, or ground, all different forms of the same radical demand and of any philosophical ‘question’)” (Derrida [2005a], p. 84). The critique of the notion of conditions of possibility includes a critique, in fine, of the motif of ground and foundation, Derrida explaining, “What is thus said of the condition of possibility also goes, by analogy, for the ‘ground,’ the ‘origin,’ the ‘root’ of ‘radicality,’ and so on” (Derrida [2005a], p. 84).

The absence of ground, as noted prior, reveals the site of the event, which is now also tied to the impossible, which Derrida (2005b) writes as im-possible: im-possible, “that is, when it is not programmed by a structure of expectation and anticipation that annuls it by making it possible and thus foreseeable” (p. 128). Therein lies Derrida’s thought of the impossible, which designates that which happens outside of the anticipating conditions of possibility of the egological subject, outside of the horizons of expectation proposed by the subject, outside of transcendental horizons of calculability. The issue is to free “the pure eventfulness of the event” (Derrida, 2003, p. 134) by breaking the power of the ego and its attempts to neutralize it. To the power of the subject as neutralization of the event, Derrida will oppose “the im-possible” as paradoxical possibility of the

event. To the whole machination of the subject, to the establishment of the power of someone, some “I can,” “to all this,” Derrida (2003) writes, “I would oppose, in the first place, everything I placed earlier under the title of the im-possible, of what must remain (in a non-negative fashion) foreign to the order of my possibilities, to the order of the ‘I can’” (p. 134). Derrida engages a deconstruction of this tradition, reversing the conditions of possibility into conditions of impossibility! It is indeed a matter of converting the possible into the impossible and recognizing that what happens arises out of the impossible. It is when “the impossible makes itself possible” that “the event takes place” as the possibility of the impossible (p. 90). It is the impossible that is possible, that happens. For Derrida (2005a), for an event to be possible, it must arise from the im-possible (it must happen as the im-possible), and not be made possible by prior conditions. In fact, it can only be an event by breaking the possible. “That, indisputably, is the paradoxical form of the event: if an event is only possible, in the classic sense of this word, if it fits in with conditions of possibility, if it only makes explicit, unveils, reveals, or accomplishes that which was already possible, then it is no longer an event. For an event to take place, for it to be possible, it has to be, as event, as invention, the coming of the impossible” (p. 90). Indeed, to make an event possible in advance is to render it impossible as an event, if it is the case that an event interrupts horizons of possibilities. It is paradoxically the condition of possibility that impossibilizes the experience of which it claims to be the condition; it is on the contrary the im-possible, as leap outside of the horizon of expectations, which possibilizes the event, the eventfulness of the event, what Derrida (2005a) calls the happening/arrival of the *arrivant* (*l’arrivée de l’arrivant*). Everything takes place as if the impossible is what truly enabled or possibilized the possible and as if the possible could only be possible as impossible. The possible “‘is’ the impossible” (Derrida, 2005a, p. 79), and in turn, the impossible is the true condition of possibility, Derrida going so far in *Rogues* (2005b) as writing of the impossible “as the only possibility and as the condition of possibility” (p. 47). The old expression of “condition of possibility” should be understood as “condition of impossibility,” undecidedly possible and impossible, possible as impossible, Derrida (2005b) often combining the two in one segment, as in “conditions of possibility or/and impossibility” (for instance, p. 49). He explains in *Paper Machine* (2005a): “As I try to show elsewhere more concretely, less formally but with more logical sequence, that requires us to think the possible . . . as the impossible.” Now, if “the possible ‘is’ the im-possible here,” then, Derrida (2005a) continues, “the ‘condition of possibility’ is a ‘condition of impossibility’” (p. 79). That thought of the event as happening from the impossible, he concludes, “has always guided me, between the possible and the impossible. This is what has so often prompted me to speak of a condition of impossibility” (Derrida, 2005a, p. 90).

Event and Cause

The deconstruction of the transcendental implies the renouncing of the reference to ground when thinking the event. Another conception of the event is called for, one no longer anchored in a cause-substrate, but happening *without ground*. With respect to causality, instead of the event following the cause, one might suggest that the event is the original phenomenon. Events do not simply follow pre-determined sequences. An event “worthy of the name” represents the surge of the new through which it precisely does not “follow” from a previous cause. A new understanding of temporality is here required: not a ruled sequence coming from the past to the present, but an eventful temporality, coming from the future, disrupting the causal networks, and transforming the entire complex of temporality, indeed transforming the past itself and our relationship to it.

Nietzsche describes an “inversion of temporality,” an *Umkehrung der Zeit*, in the process of an *a posteriori* imputation of a cause to an event. Nietzsche calls this phenomenon the error of “false causality,” which lies in the retroactive assigning of a cause to an event, an after-the-fact (re)construction that is then posited as having existed *before* the event. “I’ll begin with dreams: a particular sensation, for instance, a sensation due to a distant cannon shot, has a cause imputed to it (*untergeschoben*) afterwards (*nachträglich*).” (Nietzsche, 1997, pp, 32-33). Once the cause has been introduced, *after the event*, then, it is then said to exist prior to the event, an event that has now been transformed into necessity and meaning, a meaning that we have introduced: “In the meantime, the sensation persists in a kind of resonance: it waits, as it were, until the drive to find causes allows it to come into the foreground—not as an accident anymore, but as ‘meaning’” (p. 33). As Nietzsche explains, the sensation then becomes part of “a whole little novel in which precisely the dreamer is the protagonist.” Everyone knows the experience in a dream when the dreamer hears a sound which then becomes included in the narrative in a causal way. What was first a sheer event, perceived outside any causal network, is then integrated in the dream and reconstructed as causal origin in the narration. The event has been reconstructed and is now said to be happening *according to causality*. Of course, the cause was produced *after the fact*, and then re-injected as that from which the event occurred. “The cannon shot shows up in a *causal* way, and time seems to flow backward” (p. 33).

In fact, one must invert this inversion, and posit that the event happens *before* the cause. Only after something has happened can one begin to account for it causally. That something happens is the original fact. In that sense, there is nothing before the event. This is why Claude Romano (2009) states, in *Event and World*, “Pure beginning from nothing, an event, in its an-archic bursting forth, is absolved from all antecedent causality” (p. 41), or further: “An event has no cause, because *it is its own origin*” (p. 42).¹ It is traditionally admitted that events are determined by prior causes, and Kant (1998) insisted that “everything *that happens* presupposes a previous state, upon which it follows without exception according to a rule” (p. 484). But are we to think that events simply follow pre-determined sequences? And if this was the case, would they still be events in the proper sense? By introducing the new in the world, indeed by bringing forth a new world, does an event not disqualify prior causal contexts and networks? To that extent, an event could not be “explained” by prior events because its occurrence has transformed the very context in which it happens. Jean-Luc Marion (2002) writes: “Inasmuch as it is a given phenomenon, the event does not have an adequate cause and cannot have one. Only in this way can it advance on the wings of a dove: unforeseen, unusual, unexpected, unheard of, and unseen” (p. 167). If “innerworldly facts” can indeed be causally explained, events in the proper sense exceed causal orders. “An event is marked off from all prior facts by its very arising—coming about from itself, free of any horizon of meaning and any prior condition. An event advenes only on its own horizon. It is a pure bursting forth from and in itself, unforeseeable in its radical novelty, and retrospectively establishing a rupture with the entire past...” (Romano, 2009, p. 42).² The event happens first. The cause is added after the fact. “In summa: an event is neither effected nor does it effect. Causa

¹ In Jean-Luc Marion’s (2002) words, the event *cannot* have a cause: “Now, it happens that the event—precisely because it arises in an unpredictable landing—overcomes measure and the understanding, and therefore is excepted from all adequate cause” (p. 167).

² As Marion (2002) also explains in *Being Given*, “In taking the event as the product of a cause, one confuses it with a simple fact, added afterwards to others” (p. 165).

is a capacity to produce effects that has been super-added to the events” (Nietzsche, 1968, p. 296). There are no causes: the cause is added after the fact as an interpretation (Nietzsche [1968] speaks of an “interpretation by causality” as a “deception” [p. 296]) insofar as it is sought. The law of causality “has been projected by us into every event.”

The Event as Pure Fact

The event is a fact, an encounter, occurring outside reason. No reasons will ever measure up to the happening of the event. The event of an encounter, for instance, is not subject to the principle of sufficient reason: “An encounter is always inexplicable,” writes Gilles Deleuze (cited in Zourabichvili [2012], p. 57). To think the event is to think such absolute inexplicability and contingency. The well-known paradigm of such an encounter outside of reason is the case of friendship, such as that described by Michel de Montaigne (1958) between him and Étienne de La Boétie. “If you press me to tell why I loved him, I feel that this cannot be expressed except by answering: because it was he; because it was I [*Si on me presse de dire pourquoi je l'aimais, je sens que cela ne se peut exprimer qu'en répondant: parce que c'était lui; parce que c'était moi*]” (p. 139). As Marion (2002) comments, the event of this friendship occurs “all at once, without warning or anticipation, according to an *arrival* without expectation and without rhythm” (p. 37). The event of friendship is a fact (it “imposes itself”), a fact and a chance irreducible to reason. Therefore, no reasons will ever measure up to the fact of the encounter, to the chance happening of friendship. As Derrida (1997) puts it in *The Politics of Friendship*, “The analysis of conditions of possibility, even existential ones, will never suffice in giving an account of the act or the event. An analysis of that kind will never measure up to what takes place, the effectivity—actuality—of what comes to pass—for example, a friendship which will never be reduced to the desire or the potentiality of friendship” (p. 17). Now the notion that philosophy is born out of an event that it does not control is “a shock to reason” in its quest for ultimate foundations. For “how is it supposed to find a foundation [*assise*] in that which defeats it, in the inexplicable or the aleatory?” In the end, what transpires is that “We cannot give the reason for an event” (Zourabichvili [2012], p. 57). As Heidegger (1991) stated, “The rose is without why.... [It] ‘blooms, because it blooms’” (p. 56-57). For Heidegger, that tautology, far from saying nothing, says everything, that is, the entire *eventful facticity* of the being: it happens *because* it happens. The *because* supersedes the *why*. The event becomes the highest reason. The reason given is harbored entirely within the fact of the being, that is, within the being itself, “the fact of its being a rose or its rose-being [*ihr Rose-sein*]” (Heidegger [1991], p. 57; *Der Satz vom Grund*, GA 10, p. 84, trans. slightly modified). Jean-Luc Nancy (2007) stressed that the world, not grounded on any principle, is a *fact*; it is only a fact (even if it is a singular fact, not being itself a fact within the world). It is not founded in reason or in God. It is the fact of a “mystery,” the mystery of an accidental, errant, or wandering existence. The world is neither necessary nor contingent, if contingency is defined in relation to necessity. Rather, it would be beyond or before necessity and of contingency, an *absolute fact*. It is possible to consider this facticity of the world “without referring it to a cause (neither efficient nor final)” (p. 45). The world is a fact without cause and without reason, it is “a fact without reason or end, and it is our fact” (p. 45). We are called, in this thought of the event of the world, to take on this facticity without reason of the world, as well as its non-sense, or rather the fact that its sense only lies in such a fact: “To think it, is to think this factuality, which implies not referring it to a meaning capable of appropriating it, but to placing in it, in its truth as a fact, all possible meaning” (p. 45). The world is a significance without a foundation in reason. The world as event is without reason

and is to itself its entire possible reason.

The Impersonality of the Event

One of the constitutive errors of the metaphysical tradition is its reliance on causality, its imposition of causes on every existence, on every event, as their *substratum*: causality is the alleged substrate of the event. “Being is thought into things everywhere as a cause, is *imputed* to things” (Nietzsche [1997], p. 20). We have *created* a world of causes, a world of wills, and a world of spirits. All happening is considered a doing, all doing is supposed to be the effect of a will; the world is understood as a multiplicity of doers; a doer or subject “was imputed to everything that happened” (Nietzsche [1997], p. 32). The belief in causality thus involves the belief in the subject. Yet Nietzsche (1967) insists that one cannot attach a doer to deeds, that “there is no ‘being’ behind doing, effecting, becoming,” that the doer “is merely a fiction added to the deed” (p. 24). The notion of an underlying subjectivity is contrary to the facts, an unphenomenological construction. Instead of immediate certainties, we have the following questions: “From where do I get the concept of thinking? Why do I believe in cause and effect? What gives me the right to speak of an ego, and even of an ego as cause, and finally of an ego as the cause of thought?” (Nietzsche [1989] p. 24). All these are constructs for Nietzsche, which he understands in terms of the constitutive role of language in thinking (our thinking relies and depends on our grammar). The subject thus appears as a linguistic construct. Indeed, an underlying substantial ego is not a phenomenological fact, but a metaphysical idol, and ultimately for Nietzsche a *linguistic* prejudice. The substantialist egology of the Cartesian tradition harbors an implicit metaphysics of grammar. “One infers here according to the grammatical habit: ‘thinking is an activity; every activity requires an agent; consequently—’” (p. 24). Metaphysical idols are nothing but grammatical structures: “formerly, one believed in the soul as one believed in grammar and the grammatical subject” (p. 67). The difference between a doer and the deed, i.e., the position of an agent or subject beneath the event, is made possible by a “seduction of language” that distinguishes an agent from its deed. There is no doer, only the deed.

There is no doer. This reveals the radical *impersonality* of the event, of any event: *it* happens, of itself. This impersonality here revealed (“there is” thinking) leads us to consider subjectless sentences such as “it rains.” If the event has no subject underlying it, whether as a cause or substrate, then the danger is to substantify the “it” in such expressions, as if it designated some substrate distinct from the happening. Just as the “popular mind,” Nietzsche (1967) tells us, distinguishes the lightning from its flash, just as it reifies the “it” in the “it rains,” just as it conceives of the event as an action requiring a subject (as if behind the manifestation of strength, there was an indifferent substratum that would have the freedom to be manifest strength or not), just as it “doubles the deed” (“it posits the same event first as cause and then a second time as its effect” (p. 45), the metaphysician distinguishes a subject from its effects. In fact, Nietzsche (1967) proclaims forcefully: “there is no such substratum; there is no ‘being’ behind doing, effecting, becoming; the doer is merely a fiction added to the deed—the deed is everything” (p. 45). “The deed is everything”; this expression would require and call for another conception of the event, in which such event would no longer be anchored in a cause-substrate, but happening from itself (and yet, as we will see, happening to someone). “If I say: ‘Lightning flashes,’ I have posited the flashing once as activity and once as subject, and have thus added on to the event (*Geschehen*) a being that is not identical with the event but that *remains, is, and does not ‘become’ (nicht wird)*).

To posit the event as effecting (Wirken), and effect (Wirkung) as being: that is the twofold error, or interpretation, of which we are guilty” (Nietzsche [2003], pp. 75-76).

The event rests on no substrate, has no author; this is why it is always impersonal: *it* happens. What of this “it”? Reflecting on the impersonality of the expression *es gibt* (“it gives, “there is”) in *On Time and Being*, Heidegger (1972) notes that the risk when discussing this “it” is to posit some “indeterminate power” that somehow would cause the event (p. 16). Here again, the problem resides in the very structure of language, in a certain grammar that divides subject and predicate, and determines the “it” as a separate entity with an efficiency of its own, leading to the belief in a metaphysical substrate. As such, this grammatical structure neutralizes the eventfulness of the event. It is a matter of no longer isolating the “it” from the happening of the event. The “it” does not refer to a subject existing under the event of being, but is co-extensive with such event. If I say “it rains,” the “it” designates the *raining* itself, i.e., the *event* of raining. The “it” does not designate an underlying substrate, but designates the impersonal eventfulness of the event itself. The “it” is a stand-in for no one.

The Performative, the Letting

The event is a radically impersonal phenomenon, enacted by no one, no subject, no self: the event thus occurs *outside the subject*. As Derrida (2004) states, an event is “something that happens in some sense without or before any subject, without or before anyone’s decision” (p. 10). The event exceeds the capacity of a subject, the power of a self. This is why Derrida (2004) ultimately rejected the notion of the performative to think the event, as it still relies too heavily on the action of a subject. One often associates the performative with the enacting of an event. “We traditionally say that the performative produces events—I do what I say, I open the session if I am presiding over it, I produce the event of which I speak. In general, we thus relate the possibility of the event that is produced to a performative initiative and thus to a performative responsibility” (p. 67). However, in such a performative, the event is neutralized by the position of a powerful subject. “A performative produces an event only by securing for itself, in the first-person singular or plural, in the present, and with the guarantee offered by conventions or legitimated fictions, the power that an ipseity gives itself to produce the event of which it speaks” (Derrida [2005b], p. 152). Just like so-called “constative” or theoretical language, the performative also misses the eventful in the event. “Now, just like the constative, it seems to me, the performative cannot avoid neutralizing, indeed annulling, the eventfulness of the event it is supposed to produce” (p. 152). Certainly, Derrida (2004) concedes, something does happen with the performative, but what is eventful exceeds it: “I am not saying that nothing then happens, but what happens is programmable, foreseeable, controlled, conditioned by conventions.” Therefore, “It can thus be said, I would dare say, that an event worthy of its name is an event that derails all performativity” (p. 67). This means that it is a matter of thinking the event outside of a problematic of power, “beyond all performative mastery, beyond all power” (Derrida [2005a], p. 94), as the event undoes both will and power. An event is not a power, but what Derrida calls a “weak” or “vulnerable” force. The experience of the event “defeats my will,” writes Derrida (2007). This is why when it comes to the event, it will not be a matter of doing (involving a will and a subject), but rather of a *letting*. As Derrida (2004) writes, when it comes to the event, it is a matter of abandoning the will and *letting* the event happen, as opposed to *making* it happen (a “making happen” that always mobilizes the power and will of a subject). “Must there not be an absence of the will to abandon, whence the question of letting-

happen rather than making-happen?" (p. 92).

Indeed, once the event is no longer referred to the demands of the principle of reason, no longer anchored in a subject-cause, it becomes possible to *let* it give itself in its eventfulness, in the way it happens each time. "Thinking the event" would here mean, not subjecting it to reason, but *letting it be*. "Thinking" here should be approached as a kind of letting, letting-be or *Gelassenheit* (Heidegger [2010], p. 71). Thinking the event would mean: letting the event happen of itself, an event which itself is a kind of letting. Letting the letting be, as it were. Indeed, "letting" is for Heidegger (as it is for Derrida, as we saw above) the "deepest meaning of being" (Heidegger [2003], p.59). For an event happens *of itself*, so that an event is never prepared, produced or made, but precisely let be. To the letting of the event of being corresponds the fundamental disposition of thinking as *Gelassenheit*, as letting-be. "Thinking the event" would mean here: letting ... the letting, letting the letting be.

As the event happens *of itself*, it undoes the power of a subject, placing us, as it were, no longer in the position of actors, but, as Jean-Luc Marion (2002a) suggests, of *witnesses*. As he clarifies, the term witness signifies the undoing of the transcendental subject constituting the event as object: "With the name witness, we must understand a subjectivity stripped of the characteristics that gave it transcendental rank" (p. 217). To the constituting subject, "there follows the witness—the constituted witness" (p. 216). The event happens of itself, not constituted by a transcendental subject. The event, Marion writes, essentially is a passing; it passes and passes of itself: *Il passe et se passe*, it passes and happens of itself. Let us stress here the capital importance of the motif of passing in the thinking of the event. The event essentially *passes*. The event belongs to the fundamental category of *passing*; not "being" in the sense of a substantial presence, but *passing*. As Marion (2015) explains, "First, it is not self-evident that in order to be, a being must subsist in permanence: indeed, what is proper to the event, by definition, is not to be insofar as it subsists in permanence, but insofar *as it passes*" (p. 89; my emphasis). The event passes [*passe*] and passes of itself [*se passe*], while exceeding us from all sides. This passing passes us by. Marion writes: "The phenomenon of the passing reached me and, so to speak, constituted me as not constituting it—to the point that all I have to do is recognize myself as the mere witness (the one who certainly saw what he has seen, but does not understand what he has seen), and I renounce my claim to be its transcendental subject" (p. 186). Hence, in Waterloo, the battle "passes and passes away on its own, without anybody making it or deciding it. It passes, and each watches it pass, fade into the distance, and then disappear, disappear like it had come—that is to say, of itself" (Marion [2002a, p. 228). We, as subjects of the event, are also passing, passing and bypassed (expropriated) in the passing of the event.

The event happens of itself, is impersonal, and yet it always happens to someone, bringing forth an eventful self, that is to say, a self that is constituted (but also undone) by the event. Heidegger shows how being is an event (*Ereignis*) in which we have a part as human beings. The human being is not the *ego cogito* of the Cartesian tradition in a position of subject, but the one who is concerned by the event of being and happening from it. This new perspective requires that the self, far from designating some substantial ego or pre-given I, itself must be understood as arising from an event. In that sense, the self as such *is* an event, coming to be as a response to the eventfulness of being. It will be necessary, in our understanding of the event, to think together the impersonality of the event with the arising and responding of a self, as if the *es gibt* was the site of

an “I” to be, as called for a self that is corresponding with an otherwise im-personal phenomenon. In this respect, one ought not to be too quick to set apart the impersonality of the event with the selfhood that is engaged by it. The event is impersonal, happens of itself, but engages a self which consists precisely in the reception of such event, in which the I suffers the “shock” and trauma of the event. What is at stake here in the task of thinking the event is to reveal how the self itself is an event, happening, as it were, in and from the happening of being. The self cannot be presupposed as a pre-given or pre-constituted subject but rather originates *in and as an event*.

Conclusion: The Ethics of the Event

Ultimately, it is a matter of being hospitable to the event, of letting it come and letting it happen as it happens. The happening of the event is the coming of an *arrivant*, an arrival that is welcomed by an original hospitality. Indeed, the ethics of the event, as I approach it here, is to be taken as an ethics of hospitality, a welcome of the event in its irruptive coming. Let us focus, in closing, on this original ethics of the event. Derrida recognized in a 2004 interview with *l’Humanité* the growing importance that the thinking of the event has taken for him, significantly insisting on its ethical scope: “what you say about a privileged attention to the event is correct. It has become more and more insistent. The event, as that which happens (*arrive*) unpredictably, singularly. Not only what happens, but also who happens/arrives, the *arrivant*. The question ‘what is to be done with what/who arrives?’ commands a thinking of hospitality, of the gift, of forgiveness, of the secret, of witnessing” (Derrida and Nielsberg [2004]; my translation). We see here emerge the thematics of a hospitality to the event, an ethical welcome of the event. Such hospitality is on the side of the *arrivant*, who comes whenever it comes. Hence Derrida’s distinction between invitation and visitation. Derrida (2007) explains: “The absolute arrivant must not be merely an invited guest, someone I’m prepared to welcome, whom I have the ability to welcome. It must be someone whose unexpected, unforeseeable arrival, whose *visitation—and here I’m opposing visitation to invitation—is such an irruption that I’m not prepared to receive the person. I must not even be prepared to receive the person, for there to be genuine hospitality*” (p, 451). Invitation is the expecting of some guest, without surprise. But hospitality requires “absolute surprise”: “I must be unprepared, or prepared to be unprepared, for the unexpected arrival of any other,” and he adds: “The other, like the Messiah, must arrive whenever he or she wants” (Derrida [1999], p. 70). This, indeed, is the very definition of the event, which Derrida (2003) captures in its most limpid simplicity in this passage: “Whatever happens, happens, whoever comes, comes (*ce qui arrive arrive*), and that, in the end, is the only event worthy of this name” (p. 129).

Hospitality, then, is a receiving or welcoming that has no power over its own welcoming, it is an opening without horizon, without horizon of expectation. The event is an unforeseeable happening, affecting a vulnerable subjectivity. “If an event worthy of this name is to arrive or happen, it must, beyond all mastery, affect a passivity. It must touch an exposed vulnerability, one without absolute immunity, without indemnity; it must touch this vulnerability in its finitude and in a nonhorizontal fashion, there where it is not yet or is already no longer possible to face or face up to the unforeseeability of the other” (Derrida [2005b], p. 152). It is to this extent that Derrida understands hospitality in its full sense as unconditional. It is unconditional because it arises out of the event of the other and not from some *conditions* laid out by a subject-host. The subject is powerless before the coming of the event as *arrivant*. “The visitor is someone who could come at any moment, without any horizon of expectation, who could like the Messiah come by surprise. Anyone could come at any moment” (Derrida [2000], p.17, n. 17). Hospitality is the unconditional welcoming of the *arrivant*. “The absolute guest [*hôte*] is this *arrivant* for whom there is not even a horizon of expectation, who bursts onto my horizon of expectations when I am not even prepared to receive the one who I’ll be receiving. That’s hospitality” (Derrida [2007], p. 451). The arrival of the *arrivant* will constitute an event, says Derrida (2007), “only if I’m not capable of receiving him or her” (p. 451). Unconditional hospitality is the welcoming of such event.

Throughout this work, it has been an issue of freeing, as Derrida (2007) puts it, the “pure eventfulness of the event” (p. 134) from the traditional attempts to neutralize it, whether through the demands of a principle of reason or through the position of a willful ego.¹ As we also stressed, the event is an absolute *arrivance* (“what is true for the *arrivant* is equally true for the event” [Derrida (2007), p. 453]), which as such mobilizes a welcoming gesture. We noted the coming to the fore of the motif of “letting” in the happening of the event. This letting also affects the welcome of the event. To the letting of being (subjective genitive) corresponds the fundamental disposition of thinking as *Gelassenheit*, as letting-be. Ethics here designates such letting, a genuine *Gelassenheit* with respect to the event. This arrival is welcomed in an original hospitality, a welcome of the other in the subjective genitive. We noted throughout this work how the event happens outside knowledge, in excess of knowledge, thereby making room for another type of engagement with the event, i.e., an ethical engagement. Whereas knowledge, as Levinas claims, is a violence, ethics understood as unconditional hospitality lets the event be. Thinking the event thus leads us to an ethical engagement with its unpredictable arrival.

¹ Although, as Derrida (2007) notes, there is always an aporetic element to this question, as the event becomes each time neutralized by its reception. If on the one hand, the saying of the event “remains or should remain disarmed, utterly disarmed by ... the always unique, exceptional, and unpredictable arrival of the other, of the event as other,” yet “this disarmament, this vulnerability, and this exposure are never pure or absolute. I was saying before that the saying of the event presupposed some sort of inevitable neutralization of the event by its iterability, that saying always harbors the possibility of resaying” (p. 452).

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